

ETHICAL USE OF DIGITAL AND OTHER TECHNOLOGIES BY THE POLICE AND CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM

Nikola Dujovski

nikola.dujovski@uklo.edu.mk

Stojan Trošanski

stojantroshanski@yahoo.com

Abstract

We are living through the rise of a digitally networked society characterised by technological changes. For more than two centuries, we have faced urbanisation, factory work, labour migration, social dislocation, and a rising crime rate, that gave rise to the creation of professional public policing in the early nineteenth century. Something similar in scale may be happening nowadays and the implications for policing may be just as profound. In the modern digital era, police forces face new ethical challenges in how they use technology, requiring a focus on principles like transparency, fairness, and accountability to maintain public trust and to function as part of state authority at the same time. These principles should be embedded throughout the technology lifecycle, ensuring that innovation serves the public good and respects individual human rights.

Use of digital, scientific, and other technologies by the police and wider criminal justice system is a real challenge in today's societies. For the purposes of this research, the method of content analysis was used. It is time to face up to the challenge of policing in a digital era.

Keywords: policing; digital society; ethics; fourth industrial revolution; technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the question has been raised **as to how** the police and wider criminal justice system can best balance the potential benefits and risks of using new digital technologies. A range of new technologies are increasingly available to police services and the wider criminal justice system (CJS). Police services are already making use of new technologies for: a) crime prevention, for example predictive policing using AI to predict hotspots for future crime; b) mobility, such as autonomous vehicles and drones; c) identification and tracing, for example, automatic number plate recognition; d) surveillance and sensing, including face recognition technologies; e) analytics, using AI-enabled approaches; f) communications and interconnectivity, such as automated updates for victims or AI technology used to support call and response routing (Chief Scientific Adviser to the Police, 2024).

It's been a decade since a government programme has introduced more technology to the courts service with the aim of making the system "more straightforward, accessible and efficient" (HM Courts & Tribunals Service, 2024). This includes bringing services

online, for example, HM Courts and Tribunal Service plan to move to a new video hearings service in 2024 (Law Society, 2024).

Online, cyber-enabled, and AI-enabled crime show an increasing tendency. For example, developments in fraud, grooming and ‘sextortion’, stalking, and ransomware incidents have direct implications for crime prevention, investigation and emphasized victim support. Perpetrators of online crimes may be harder to identify and can operate from any location. The Online Safety Act 2023 in the United Kingdom introduced new criminal offences from January 2024, including cyberflashing, threatening communications and intimate image abuse (Office for National Statistics (2022); The Times (2024); Todd, C. et al. (2020); Cross, C. et al. (2022); Horgan, S (2021); Correia, S. G. (2022); Scheurman, M.K. et al. Caton, S. and Landman, R. (2021); Ryan, F. (2019); Department for Science, Innovation & Technology (2024); Metropolitan Police, 2025).

Digitalization requires new spheres and ways of acting, a different nature of action in the work of state bodies engaged in crime prevention, and raising awareness about ethics in the application of technology today.

2. CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN TODAY'S TIME

Government, police forces, and other sector stakeholders have noted potential benefits to using new technologies in the criminal justice system: a) improving performance, for example, in preventing and detecting crime, using Facial Recognition Technology (FRT) to identify criminals; b) improving efficiency by freeing up police time and capacity for higher priority work; c) making it easier for individuals and communities to communicate and interact with the police services; d) supporting transparency, accountability and trust (House of Lords Justice and Home Affairs Committee (2022); Guzik, K. et al. (2019); Higgins, A. and Halkon, R. (2023); HM Courts & Tribunals Service (2024); The Standard (2023); McGuire, M. R. (2020); EAW Coalition (2023); Orell, C. (2023); Justice Committee (2022); Home Affairs Committee (2021); Lum, C. et al. (2020); Bradford, B., et al. (2022)).

Parliamentary, academic and sector stakeholders debate several areas of concern or risk arising from the introduction of new technologies. There has been public discussion about how the police and CJS must balance the rights of individuals with societal safety in introducing new technologies. An independent report for the Scottish government emphasised the importance of “a rights based, ethical, evidence-based, consultative approach to innovation and adoption of emerging technologies in policing, within a robust oversight framework” (Fontes, C. and Perrone, C. (2021); Aston, E. (2023)).

The aspects discussed relate to the following significant points:

- ethical and human rights, civil liberties and the right to a fair trial;
- data protection;
- validity and accuracy of technologies;
- risks around equality and discrimination;
- right to privacy, for example, from access to smart doorbell footage (Aston, E. (2023); Almeida, D. et al. (2022); BBC News (2020)).

Debate has already arisen in relation to police use of facial recognition technology (FRT). Academics and civil liberties groups have raised multiple concerns, including the imposition of FRT and its impact on privacy rights, and a lack of oversight, accountability and transparency. There is particular debate about the relative accuracy of FRT for different demographic groups, and the risk that its use exacerbates discrimination. A 2023

National Physical Laboratory evaluation for the Metropolitan Police Service (in the United Kingdom) found no differences in accuracy of identification by age, gender or ethnicity for Retrospective or Operator-Initiated FRT. However, for Live FRT, it found some differences in accuracy for people aged under 20 years old and for Black subjects, with lower face-match thresholds. (Lower thresholds mean the FRT system is less strict, increasing the risk of matching an innocent person with an individual on an offender watchlist) (McDonald, N. et al (2020); Radiya-Dixit, E (2022); Mansfield, T. (2023)).

The Chief Scientific Adviser to the Police, and academic commentators, have noted that maintaining public trust remains a major challenge to the introduction of technology and have emphasized the importance of public communication and transparency. Researchers have also highlighted the potential links between public trust in new technology and ‘policing by consent’, securing legitimacy and public compliance and cooperation. In particular, little is known about the impact of the existing use of technology in police-public interactions (for example, chatbots for crime reporting, social media engagement with communities, and body-worn cameras) on ‘policing by consent’ (Laufs, J. and Borrión, H. (2022); Aston, E. et al. (2021); Aston, E. et al. (2022); Wells, H. et al. (2022)).

A 2022 Justice and Home Affairs Committee report on the use of new technologies in the CJS also highlighted challenges around lack of oversight, regulation, scrutiny of application and information on what is being used, where, and how. It, supported by research, noted the potential role of data ethics committees. There are also existing challenges to AI governance, including around bias, privacy, consent and transparency of algorithms ([Artificial Intelligence in policing and security](#)). In 2023, the government proposed to abolish the role of the Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner (BSCC), and its governance and oversight responsibilities, through the Data Protection and Digital Information Bill. An independent report suggested that the abolition could leave gaps in future oversight. However, the bill did not progress before the July 2024 election. The incumbent BSCC resigned in mid-August 2024 (Charlesworth, A. et al. (2023); Oswald, M. et al (2024); Science, Innovation and Technology Committee (2024); Fussey, P. and Webster, W. (2023); Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner (2023); UK Parliament (2024); Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner (2023)).

The Justice and Home Affairs Committee, and other stakeholders, have raised concerns about how well procurement and the market for AI technologies work, for example in terms of consistency of purchasing, user knowledge of products, selling practices, and security concerns about suppliers. For example, a research study noted that a lack of consistent and transparent standards for the use of computer algorithms in technology used by the police could increase the risk of bias in their use, increase costs and inefficiencies, and lower public trust and acceptability.

In relation to digital forensics, another study found that the need to keep pace with technological advances had significant implications for purchase and maintenance costs, and ensuring user compliance and accreditation. It recommended a review of whether strategic investment in policing co-access to equipment and personnel would help address such challenges. The independent report for the Scottish government included recommendations around improving business cases and evidence assessments for new technologies, adopting appropriate standards, and developing a public operational practice code (Zilka, M., et al. (2023) & Griffiths, C. et al. (2024)).

There are also significant challenges around securing the right, and enough, workforce skills to deploy new technologies, whether operated by experts or non-specialists. The Justice and Home Affairs Committee recommended better training for staff on the legislative context, the risk of bias, and how to use the tools. Research studies note further internal barriers to adopting new technology, including migration to new systems, securing financial and political support, and unclear guidelines and procedures.

The growing role of technology in crime, and the increase in online, artificial intelligence- and cyber-enabled crime means the police must increasingly process and analyse digital material and evidence quickly. This can include text, media and metadata; footage from video, smart doorbells, smartphones, and social media; and materials from developing platforms such as virtual reality, online gaming, and the metaverse. Academic studies report challenges around the scale of demand for these digital forensic examinations and how best to manage the rising demand. For the court service, the Justice Committee noted in 2022 that there were delays to the government's programme, and a lack of data and analysis to establish the effectiveness of the programme. The Committee found that, despite potential benefits for efficiency and public/media access, the use of online procedures and digitisation in courts may have reduced transparency, and resulted in variations in accessibility and information quality (Griffiths, C. et al. (2024); Sandhu, A. and Fussey, P. (2020); Rappert, B. et al. (2020); Justice Committee (2022)).

3. THE "SAFE CITY" PROJECT IN NORTH MACEDONIA

The Safe City system and the installed cameras will start operating on 1 January of next year. The Ministry of Internal Affairs (MIA) will have enough time to record all newly registered vehicles and coordinate the data with other institutions, in order to precisely determine the method of punishment. Drivers who commit a violation will receive an SMS or e-mail with a photo of the violation within 24 hours. The police are already testing the installed cameras throughout Skopje. The most common violations are exceeding the speed limit and driving through a red light.

To establish the Safe City system, it was necessary to amend several laws, including:

- The Law on Road Traffic Safety, to enable automatic monitoring and sanctioning through cameras and sensors,
- The Law on Misdemeanours, to define a new method for recording and processing misdemeanours through digital systems,
- Law on Vehicles, to enable the collection of additional data during registration (phone number, email address),
- The Law on Enforcement of Sanctions, to enable the automatic enforcement of penalties and notifications through electronic systems, Criminal Code, to harmonize certain misdemeanours with criminal procedures, especially in cases of recurrence or dangerous behaviour.

The preparations for the start of operations are in their final phase, and estimates indicate that everything will be ready by the scheduled date for the launch of the new traffic penalty policy. At this very stage, all inconsistencies must be resolved, with particular attention given to ethical implementation and, above all, the respect for human freedoms and rights. Since this is a sensitive process being introduced for the first time in our country, it is essential that citizens are fully and timely informed and that they trust the system will operate without compromising any human rights.

Digital tools and video surveillance systems are useful instruments in police work and contribute to improving public safety. However, their use must remain strictly within

legally defined boundaries, as it is very easy for procedures to be initiated that could undermine the system and diminish public trust in these new practices of monitoring citizens' movements.

In addition to Skopje, the system will also be implemented in several other major urban areas, such as Kumanovo and Tetovo, and almost simultaneously along the highway section from Tabanovce to Bogorodica.

3.1. New traffic rules for fines for pedestrians and drivers for using phones and headphones will come into effect from September 26th.

The end of riding scooters with headphones in your ears or crossing pedestrians with a phone in your ear has come. The law has been published in the Official Gazette and from September 26th, stricter provisions will begin to apply to road users who will be fined for paying attention to electronic devices instead of driving. Crossing a pedestrian while using a mobile phone will be fined 40 euros, and for drivers of scooters, tractors, motorcycles who both drive and use electronic devices, the fine is 50 euros.

"Safe City" has been legalized and is already being used on a trial basis and for analysis, and with its help, striking numbers of traffic violations are being detected. Although it is included in the amendments to the Traffic Safety Law, the cameras from "Safe City" will be used for fines from the New Year. However, from September 26, the amendment will already apply to pedestrians who will not be allowed to cross streets with a mobile phone to their ear and talking because the law states that the fine is 40 euros for that violation.

"A pedestrian is obliged, when moving on a roadway under the conditions established by this law or when crossing the roadway and the bicycle path or bicycle lane, to move and cross carefully, without using electronic devices, such as headphones, a mobile phone, tablet, smart watch or other type of electronic device, which would reduce his attention while crossing the roadway and the bicycle path or bicycle lane," states Article 116-a of the Traffic Safety Law.

There will be fines for those who ride scooters, as well as for tractor drivers and cyclists if they use mobile devices or have headphones in their ears while driving. The fine for this is 50 euros.

Half a per mille of alcohol in the blood remains as the definition of drunk driving, except that for the most drunk, that is, those who have over one and a half per mille of alcohol, the fine will be 375 euros and a driving ban of 9 months to one year. The law allows the police to use much greater types of video surveillance, including "Safe City".

"The police are authorized to install technical means and devices for recording in public places where traffic is carried out and where road traffic offenses may be committed, i.e. the use of video surveillance and systems that use advanced technology in order to document traffic offenses, the manner of committing them, detect perpetrators and monitor safety and traffic flow, in accordance with the jurisdiction established by law," states Article 369 of the Traffic Safety Law. In order for Safe City to function, the law on misdemeanours, which has not yet been reviewed by the MPs and has not been fully written, should also be passed in the same package, and changes should also be made to three other laws.

CONCLUSION

The introduction of new technologies is a "double-edged sword." In the short term, the first results can be expected that will serve as a roadmap for the direction in which the security system should be organized so that society can function normally and safely, and thus the police service can perform its task without hindrance.

The Safe City system is not something new on a global scale. It also operates in other countries, especially in Europe (most countries have implemented similar systems over recent decades, including our neighbouring countries Serbia and Bulgaria) and on the Asian continent.

It must be noted that in this sphere, there is a thin line between normal and free on the one hand, and restrictive and illogical on the other, when it comes to the rules and algorithms according to which this system functions. The system itself, as such, is completely harmless, but in the hands of unethical professionals who would insert wrong algorithms that do not correspond to natural laws, it can very easily get out of control and contribute to unwanted effects.

Morality and ethics are an inseparable *conditio sine qua non* element of this issue.

REFERENCES

1. Almeida, D. et al. (2022). [The ethics of facial recognition technologies, surveillance, and accountability in an age of artificial intelligence: a comparative analysis of US, EU, and UK regulatory frameworks](#) AI Ethics, Vol 2, 377–387.
2. Aston, E. (2023). [Independent review – Independent advisory group on new and emerging technologies in policing: final report](#) Scottish Government.
3. Aston, E. et al. (2021). [Information sharing in community policing in Europe: Building public confidence](#) European Journal of Criminology, 20(4), 1349-1368.
4. Aston, E. et al. (2022). [Technology and Police Legitimacy](#) in Verhage, A. et al. (eds) Policing in Smart Societies. Palgrave's Critical Policing Studies. Palgrave Macmillan.
5. Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner (2023). [Report finds 'worrying vacuum' in surveillance camera plans](#) GOV.UK.
6. Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner (2023). [Resignation of the Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner](#) GOV.UK.
7. Bradford, B., et al. (2022). ['Virtual policing', trust and legitimacy](#) in Terpstra, J. et al (Eds.), The Abstract Police: Critical reflections on contemporary change in police organisations (213-238).
8. Caton, S. and Landman, R. (2021). [Internet safety, online radicalisation and young people with learning disabilities](#) British Journal of Learning Disabilities, Volume 50, Issue 1, pp: 88–97.
9. Chief Scientific Adviser to the Police. [Policing Areas of Research Interest Version 0.1](#) Accessed 11 October 2024.
10. Charlesworth, A. et al. (2023). [Response to the UK's March 2023 White Paper "A pro-innovation approach to AI regulation"](#) SSRN.
11. Correia, S. G. (2022). [Making the most of cybercrime and fraud crime report data: a case study of UK Action Fraud](#), International Journal of Population Data Science, 7(1).
12. Cross, C. et al. (2022). ["If U Don't Pay they will Share the Pics": Exploring Sextortion in the Context of Romance Fraud](#) Victims & Offenders, 18(7), 1194–1215.

- [13. Department for Science, Innovation & Technology \(2024\). Online Safety Act: explainer.](#)
- [14. EAW Coalition \(2023\). Listen to us! Communication Barriers: How Statutory Bodies are failing Black, minoritized, Migrant, Deaf & Disabled Women and Girls Victims/Survivors of VAWG.](#)
- [15. Fontes, C. and Perrone, C. \(2021\). Ethics of surveillance: harnessing the use of live facial recognition technologies in public spaces for law enforcement](#) Institute for Ethics in Artificial Intelligence, Technical University of Munich.
- [16. Fussey, P. and Webster, W. \(2023\). Changes to the functions of the BSCC: independent report \(accessible\) Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner, GOV.UK.](#)
- [17. Griffiths, C. et al. \(2024\). The Northumbria University Digital Forensics Project. Digital Forensics within the Criminal Justice System – Use, Effectiveness and Impact Northumbria University report.](#)
- [18. Guzik, K. et al. \(2019\). Making the material routine: a sociomaterial study of the relationship between police body worn cameras \(BWCs\) and organisational routines Policing and Society: Vol 31, No 1: Policing and Technology.](#)
- [19. Higgins, A. and Halkon, R. \(2023\). Contact and Confidence in a Digital Age: Improving police-public relations with technology Police Foundation.](#)
- [20. HM Courts & Tribunals Service \(2024\). The HMCTS Reform Programme.](#)
- [21. HM Courts & Tribunals Service \(2024\). Fact sheet: Single Justice Service.](#)
- [22. House of Lords Justice and Home Affairs Committee \(2022\). Technology Rules? The advent of new technologies in the justice system.](#)
- [23. Home Affairs Committee \(2021\). The Macpherson Report: twenty-one years on UK Parliament.](#)
- [24. Horgan, S \(2021\). SJF Briefing: The reality of ‘cyber awareness’: findings and policy implications for Scotland The Scottish Centre for Crime & Justice Research.](#)
- [25. Justice Committee \(2022\). Open justice: court reporting in the digital age UK Parliament.](#)
- [26. Justice Committee \(2022\). Court Capacity UK Parliament.](#)
- [27. Laufs, J. and Borrión, H. \(2022\). Technological innovation in policing and crime prevention: Practitioner perspectives from London International Journal of Police Science & Management, 24\(2\), 190-209.](#)
- [28. Law Society \(2024\). Remote hearings.](#)
- [29. Lum, C. et al. \(2020\). Body-worn cameras’ effects on police officers and citizen behavior: A systematic review Campbell Systematic Reviews, Volume 16, Issue 3.](#)
- [30. Mansfield, T. \(2023\). Facial Recognition Technology in Law Enforcement, Equitability Study Final Report National Physical Laboratory.](#)
- [31. McDonald, N. et al \(2020\). Privacy and Power: Acknowledging the Importance of Privacy Research and Design for Vulnerable Populations in Extended Abstracts of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems \(CHI EA ’20\), 1-8. Association for Computing Machinery.](#)
- [32. McGuire, M. R. \(2020\). The laughing policebot: automation and the end of policing Policing and Society: Vol 31, No 1: Policing and Technology.](#)
- [14. Metropolitan Police. Turnaround Plan 2023-2025.](#)
- [33. Orell, C. \(2023\). Use of Augmentative and Alternative Communication in Police Interviews All Voices.](#)

34. Oswald, M. et al (2024). [Ethical review to support Responsible Artificial Intelligence \(AI\) in policing: A preliminary study of West Midlands Police’s specialist data ethics review committee.](#)
35. Science, Innovation and Technology Committee (2024). [Governance of artificial intelligence \(AI\)](#) UK Parliament.
36. POST. 25 October, 2024 Horizon scanning. Use of digital, scientific and other technologies by the police and wider criminal justice system. Accessed via (<https://post.parliament.uk/use-of-digital-scientific-and-other-technologies-by-the-police-and-wider-criminal-justice-system/>).
37. Radiya-Dixit, E (2022). [A Sociotechnical Audit: Assessing Police use of Facial Recognition](#) Minderoo Centre for Technology and Democracy.
38. Rappert, B. et al. (2020). [Rationing bytes: managing demand for digital forensic examinations](#) Policing and Society: Vol 31, No 1: Policing and Technology.
39. Ryan, F. (2019). [Online abuse of disabled people is getting worse – when will it be taken seriously?](#) The Guardian.
40. Sandhu, A. and Fussey, P. (2020). [The ‘uberization of policing’? How police negotiate and operationalise predictive policing technology](#) Policing and Society: Vol 31, No 1: Policing and Technology.
41. Scheuerman, M.K. et al. (2021). [A Framework of Severity for Harmful Content Online](#), Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction, Volume 5, Issue CSCW2.
42. See for example the following reports and articles: Office for National Statistics (2022). [Nature of fraud and computer misuse in England and Wales: year ending March 2022](#); UK Finance (2022). [Over £1.2 billion stolen through fraud in 2022, with nearly 80 per cent of APP fraud cases starting online](#); NSPCC (2022). [Online grooming crimes have risen by more than 80% in four years](#); Home Office (2021). [Tackling violence against women and girls strategy](#); National Cyber Security Centre and National Crime Agency (2023). [Ransomware, extortion and the cyber crime ecosystem](#) White paper.
43. See for example the following media articles: The Times (2024). [Police investigate death of teenager targeted by online blackmail](#); BBC News (2016). [Bid to extradite man over Daniel Perry ‘sextortion’ death](#); Washington Post (2024). [Bobbi Althoff deepfake spotlights X’s role as a top source of AI porn](#); The Guardian (2024). [Anyone could be a victim of ‘deepfakes’. But there’s a reason Taylor Swift is a target.](#)
44. See for example the following media articles: BBC News (2020). [FBI worried that Ring doorbells are spying on police](#); The Independent (2024). [Amazon’s Ring stops programme to hand doorbell camera footage to police](#); BBC News (2023). [Video doorbells: Police champion them but do they cut crime?.](#)
45. The Standard (2023). [Facial recognition vans: the case for and against.](#)
46. Todd, C. et al. (2020). [Technology, cyberstalking and domestic homicide: informing prevention and response strategies](#), Policing and Society, 31(1), 82–99.
47. UK Parliament (2024). [Data Protection and Digital Information Bill.](#)
48. Wells, H. et al. (2022). [‘Channel shift’: Technologically mediated policing and procedural justice](#) International Journal of Police Science & Management, Volume 25, Issue 1.
49. Zilka, M., et al. (2023). [Exploring Police Perspectives on Algorithmic Transparency: A Qualitative Analysis of Police Interviews in the UK](#) in EAAMO ’23: Proceedings of the 3rd ACM Conference on Equity and Access in Algorithms, Mechanisms, and Optimization Association for Computing Machinery.